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A Universal Dependencies Treebank for Nheengatu

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Abstract

We present UD_Nheengatu-CompLin, the inaugural treebank for Nheengatu, an endangered Indigenous language of Brazil with limited digital resources. This treebank stands as the largest among Indigenous American languages in version 2.13 of the Universal Dependencies collection. The developmental version comprises 1,336 trees, encompassing 13,246 tokens and 13,374 words. In a 10-fold cross-validation experiment using UDPipe 1.2, parsing with gold tokenization and gold tags achieved a labeled attachment score (LAS) of 81.17 ± 1.02 , outperforming Yauti, the rule-based analyzer employed for sentence annotation.

1 Introduction

Universal Dependencies (henceforth UD) provides a framework for consistent morphosyntactic annotation across languages of different families, aiming at both linguistic typology and natural language processing (Nivre et al., 2016; de Marneffe et al., 2021). The UD collection has grown from 10 treebanks of 10 European languages in version 1.0 of January 2015 to 259 treebanks of 148 languages from all continents in version 2.13 of November 2023 (Zeman et al., 2023). However, the enormous diversity of Indigenous languages in the Americas is still underrepresented despite the efforts in the last five years.¹

This paper introduces UD_Nheengatu-CompLin, the first UD treebank for Nheengatu (ISO 639-3: yr1), an endangered Indigenous language of Brazil, also known as Modern Tupi and *Língua Geral Amazônica* (hereafter LGA). Although it made its debut in UD v2.11 on November 15, 2022, with only 196 trees, it has since expanded significantly. With 1,239 trees totaling 12,621 tokens, it stands

¹Following the recommendations in *The Chicago Manual of Style Online* (2024) and elsewhere, we capitalize *Indigenous* in the sense used in this paper.

as the largest treebank for an Indigenous American language in UD v2.13. To our knowledge, no analogous resource for Nheengatu exists. It is made available under a license.

2 Related work

Wagner et al. (2016) adapted the UD annotation guidelines to Arapaho, an Algonquian language spoken in Wyoming, USA. Shipibo-Konibo, however, seems to have been the first Indigenous American language with a treebank under the UD framework (Vasquez et al., 2018).² There followed Mbya Guaraní (Thomas, 2019), Yupik (Park et al., 2021), K'iche' (Tyers and Henderson, 2021), Apurinã (Rueter et al., 2021), Nahuatl (Pugh et al., 2022), Tupinamba, and ten other languages, mostly Tupian of Brazil (Martín Rodríguez et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2024). As expected of treebanks for low-resource languages, they are “opportunistic corpora” (McEnery and Hardie, 2012, p. 11) with no reported inter-annotator agreement.

Parsing experiments with these treebanks showed that performance is heavily dependent on factors like gold part-of-speech (POS) tags and training data size. For instance, parsing Shipibo-Konibo with gold POS tags yielded a labeled attachment score (LAS) of 81.25 ± 3.45 , while parsing raw text resulted in a score of 30.39 ± 1.34 , indicating a significant drop in performance (Vasquez et al., 2018). This is not surprising given the small size of the treebank with only 407 trees and 2,706 tokens. Similarly, for the Nahuatl treebank, which had a larger size of 10,356 tokens and 939 trees, UDPipe 1 (Straka et al., 2016; Straka and Straková, 2017) was used to obtain a LAS score of 68.1 ± 2.0 with normalized text (Pugh et al., 2022).

Nheengatu, with a Digital Language Support Level of only 0.07 (Simons et al., 2022; Eberhard

²This treebank has never been part of any release of the UD collection. Instead, the UD homepage lists it among the “possible future extensions”.

et al., 2023), is among many minority languages impacted by the digital divide, despite recent initiatives. For example, da Rocha D'Angelis et al. (2021) discusses the localization of a smartphone operating system for Nheengatu. However, this system does not provide any text input enhancement technologies, e.g., word completion, spelling correction, etc. After summarizing previous directly related work, de Alencar (2023) proposes a tool called Yauti for the UD annotation of Nheengatu. Cavalin et al. (2023) included Nheengatu in a study of language identification.

3 Nheengatu, the “good language”

Nheengatu originated in the 17th century in Maranhão from Tupinamba, one of the many varieties of Tupi, which was dominant along the Brazilian coast in the 16th century (Edelweiss, 1969; Borges, 1996; Rodrigues, 1996; Freire, 2011; Rodrigues and Cabral, 2011; Navarro, 2012; Finbow, 2023). The Portuguese colonizers adopted Tupi as *língua geral*, i.e. lingua franca, of which other varieties besides the LGA developed (de Lurdes Zanolli, 2022; Leite, 2013). Description and teaching of Tupi, e.g., Anchieta (1595); Figueira (1621), were incumbent on Jesuits (Edelweiss, 1969; de Almeida Navarro, 2009; Altman, 2022). Not Portuguese, but Tupi was Brazil's de facto first national language (Drumond, 1964). It was widespread among black Africans as well as Europeans and their descendants of Indigenous women, some of these mixed families attaining high economic status and social prestige (Moore, 2014). Seixas (1853) is the earliest known usage of the term *Nheengatu* ‘good language’ to designate the LGA.

A Royal Charter of 1689 made Tupi the official language of the State of Maranhão and Grão-Pará until an analogous document in 1727 prohibited it in favor of the Portuguese language (Moore, 2014). However, as D'Angelis (2023) points out, the mere existence of a document stating a preference for a particular language does not necessarily guarantee its widespread adoption. In fact, by 1750, except for some colonial administrators who came from Portugal, the LGA was still the predominant language spoken throughout the colony (Moore, 2014). It continuously spread along the Amazon River and its tributaries, like the Rio Negro, eventually reaching Colombia and Venezuela. In the middle of the 19th century, the LGA was the most widely spoken language in the Brazilian Amazon, including larger

cities such as Belém. Documentation of Nheengatu boomed from this time until the early 20th century (Altman, 2022). On the one hand, emperor Pedro II promoted field research on Nheengatu, which resulted in the publication of oral Nheengatu literature and grammars, e.g., de Magalhães (1876). On the other, Nheengatu was part of the curriculum of the Seminary of Belém, and Church representatives produced teaching materials (Seixas, 1853; Aguiar, 1898; Costa, 1909).

The *Cabanagem* revolt (1835-1845) and mass immigration from the Northeast starting in 1877, among other factors, triggered Nheengatu's continual decline (Navarro et al., 2017). Today, as a first language, it is limited to São Gabriel da Cachoeira in the Upper Rio Negro, where it is co-official, having replaced the original non-Tupi Arawak languages of the Bare, Baniwa, and Warekena, whose languages are extinct or moribund (Eberhard et al., 2023). Nheengatu itself, with reportedly 6000 speakers in Brazil and 8000 in Colombia, where it ranks 6b and 7 on the EGIDS scale, respectively, is severely endangered, being “nearly extinct” in Venezuela, with 8b status and “[v]ery few, if any, speakers left” (Eberhard et al., 2023). Nheengatu as a contact language has also dramatically diminished (Finbow, 2020). Fortunately, diverse revitalization initiatives, e.g., in the Middle Amazon River (Lima Schwade, 2021) and the Lower Tapajós River, have targeted Nheengatu (Silva Meirelles, 2020). Besides, Indigenous people whose original languages have long gone extinct, from places as far away from the Amazon region as the Ceará State, are learning Nheengatu to affirm their ethnic identity (Filho, 2010). In 2021, the Monsenhor Tabosa municipality in Ceará adopted “Tupinheengatu” as a co-official language (Government, 2021).

All this background places Nheengatu in a unique position among the approximately 150 Indigenous languages that are still alive in Brazil, according to Storto (2019). Unlike any other, Nheengatu is supra-ethnic and has never been a tribal language (Borges, 1996; Navarro, 2012). Its influence on Brazilian Portuguese is unparalleled (de Souza Martins, 2012, 2014). Not only that, but Nheengatu has also had a significant impact on intellectuals of the stature of Mario de Andrade, Villa-Lobos, and Guimarães Rosa (Avila and Trevisan, 2015; Campoi, 2015; Pucci, 2017; Toni and Fresca, 2022). Moore (2014, p. 108) states: “Nheengatu has a notable charm. People

delight in learning it and regard it with affection.” Indeed, since the last decade, non-Indigenous learners have contributed significantly to the stock of texts in Nheengatu, e.g., by translating literary classics such as Graciliano Ramos, Saint-Exupéry, and Tolstoy (Avila, 2016; Trevisan, 2017; Costa, 2019). August 2023 marked a significant milestone: the Federal Supreme Court and the National Council of Justice published a translation of the Brazilian Constitution into Nheengatu (Lucchesi et al., 2023), making it the first Indigenous language to receive such an honor.

4 Overview of the treebank

Sentence lengths in the UD_Nheengatu-CompLin treebank range from 2 to approximately 50 words (Figure 1), with a mean and median of 10.01 and 8.0 words, respectively, and a standard deviation of 6.72, reflecting the richness found in Nheengatu texts, as represented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of sentence length in the treebank.

Table 2 presents statistics for the current development version, calculated using UD’s `conllu-stats.pl` script. It includes corresponding data from UD_Guajajara-TuDeT (Gerardi et al., 2022; Martín Rodríguez et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2024), the second-largest treebank for a Brazilian Indigenous language in the UD collection. Guajajara also pertains to the Tupian family. The Nheengatu treebank surpasses the Guajajara in most dimensions (Section 4.4).

The second column of Table 1 contains the first field of the sentence identifier (Section 4.1).³ About half of the sentences stem from Avila (2021),

³NTLN2019 = do Brasil (2019), MooreFP1994 = Moore et al. (1994), TerraPreta2013 = Bird et al. (2013), Stradelli2014 = Stradelli (1929, 2014), DLGA2019 = Müller et al. (2019).

Freq.	Source	Rel. Freq.
705	Avila2021	0.5273
216	Navarro2016	0.1617
86	Magalhaes1876	0.0644
61	Cruz2011	0.0457
56	Alencar2021	0.0420
48	NTLN2019	0.0360
46	Rodrigues1890	0.0345
38	MooreFP1994	0.0285
23	Casasnovas2006	0.0173
23	Amorim1928	0.0173
16	Sympson1877	0.0120
7	TerraPreta2013	0.0052
3	Aguiar1909	0.0022
2	Stradelli2014	0.0015
2	Melgueiro2022	0.0015
2	DLGA2019	0.0015
1	Seixas1853	0.0007
1	Hartt1938	0.0007
1336	Total	1.0000

Table 1: Frequency of treebank examples per bibliographical source.

on which we have mostly based the selection of sources. With circa 8,000 lemmas and 4,000 unique examples, this is certainly the most comprehensive dictionary of a Brazilian Indigenous language, perhaps only rivaled by Navarro’s (2015) dictionary of Ancient Tupi. The entries have a rich microstructure covering semantic, grammatical, and etymological aspects, anchored in a wide-coverage research of practically all known sources of Nheengatu from the 18th to the 21st century.

Making up 16% of the treebank, the second largest group of sentences derives from de Almeida Navarro (2016). This is a self-contained coursebook with 13 lessons containing both constructed and authentic contemporary as well as historical texts, accompanied by didactic translations into Portuguese. The lessons follow a grammatical progression that facilitates the annotation. The treebank presently covers almost all examples up to the 4th lesson. Sympson (1877); Casasnovas (2006) are two other important coursebooks (Table 1).

The 3rd portion of the treebank derives from de Magalhães (1876), perhaps the most influential oeuvre of 19th-century Nheengatu literature. Rodrigues (1890); de Amorim (1928) contain analogous collections of fables and myths. da Cruz

Treebank	Sentences	Words	Lemmas	Forms	Fusions	Features	Dependency Relations
Nheengatu	1336	13374	1244	1707	89	71	36
Guajajara	1182	9160	593	1314	138	72	29

Table 2: Comparison of statistics between UD_Nheengatu-CompLin and UD_Guajajara-TuDeT.

(2011) makes up the 4th portion. This is the most comprehensive description of the phonology and grammar of 21st-century Nheengatu as spoken by the Bare, Baniwa, and Warekena in the Upper Rio Negro. The 5th treebank portion consists of a sample from the test set of constructed sentences expressing a qualifying predication, as described in de Alencar (2021). Diverse studies have shown the importance of biblical texts for NLP (McCarthy et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021). An indispensable textual resource documenting late 20th-century Nheengatu is the New Testament translation (do Brasil, 2019), of which the treebank features 92 sentences. 44 stem from Avila (2021). We manually extracted and adapted the other 48 sentences (Table 1), such a limited number being due to annotation difficulties. The treebank contains all 38 sentences from Moore et al. (1994), a concise but fairly complete description of Nheengatu phonology and grammar based on the transcribed speech of two native speakers from the Upper Rio Negro. The examples show to what extent Nheengatu changed structurally towards Portuguese and to what extent it remained true to Tubinamba.

The treebank only contains a few examples from textual materials by Indigenous writers, e.g., Bird et al. (2013); Filho and Neto (2016); da Silva et al. (2021); Yamã et al. (2021); Melgueiro (2022) (Table 1). Incorporating more extensive passages beyond what would be considered fair use requires permission from authors. We are already contacting some of them about this.

Our ultimate goal with the treebank is to acknowledge the linguistic significance, cultural richness, and social relevance of Nheengatu, encompassing all the texts from the 19th and early 20th centuries that are in the public domain, e.g., Seixas (1853); Hartt (1872); de Magalhães (1876); Symson (1877); Rodrigues (1890); Aguiar (1898); Costa (1909); de Amorim (1928); Stradelli (1929); Hartt (1938). Apart from copyright restrictions, contemporary texts pose greater challenges to morphosyntactic annotation in the context of UD due to a lack of interlinear glossing or suitable transla-

Figure 2: Dependency tree of (1) highlighting the features of the verb form *resasá*.

tions. They also exhibit strong orthographic variation and grammatical or lexical idiosyncrasies. We aim to overcome these challenges by involving Indigenous speakers with a background in linguistics in the sentence annotation workflow.

4.1 Metadata

UD does not specify a rigid scheme for metadata. The official `validate.py` script only requires the CoNLL-U files of a treebank to have two attributes: `text` and `sent_id` (Conllu). Therefore, one encounters great variability in the types and names of metadata attributes in the validated treebanks of the UD collection. In our treebank, sentences additionally have the obligatory attributes `text_eng`, `text_por`, `text_source` and `text_annotator`, which encode the English and Portuguese translations, the source of the sentence, and the annotator (Figure 2).⁴ Unless otherwise noted, we use, if available, the translation provided in the same publication we extracted the Nheengatu example from, translating it to English or Portuguese as appropriate.

`sent_id` is a unique sentence identifier, consisting of four colon-separated pieces of information, namely, (i) an abbreviation keying to the publication the sentence stems from, (ii) an integer identifying a complete text or a continuous text fragment

⁴The graph of Figure 2 was produced with <https://urd2.let.rug.nl/~kleiweg/conllu/>.

within the publication, (iii) a sequencing index for the sentence in this text, and (iv) a count number for the sentences from the same source. Examples (1)–(3) help clarify this. In (1) (respectively Figure 2) and (2), Avila2021 refers to Avila (2021).⁵ The third and second field in (1) and (2) identify the first two sentences of the 51st text fragment of the treebank stemming from Avila (2021), which are the 688th and 689th sentence from this source. In (3), 1:2 designates the second sentence of the first myth of de Magalhães (1876).

- (1) — *Maita resasá?* ‘How are you?’ (Avila2021:51:1:688) (de Magalhães, 1876, p. 89)
- (2) — *Se katuntu.* ‘I’m just fine.’ (Avila2021:51:2:689) (de Magalhães, 1876, p. 89)
- (3) *Pituna ukiri uikú í ripí-pe.* ‘The night was sleeping at the bottom of the water.’ (Magalhães1876:1:2:2)

In case of isolated sentences, the second and third fields are set to 0, see (4)–(6). Example (4) actually stems from a story but is cited without any additional context.

- (4) *Yepé paá uwapika igara gantime, amú uwapika yakumame.* ‘It is said that one was sitting in the bow of the canoe, the other was sitting in the stern.’ (Avila2021:0:0:342) (Casasnovas, 2006, p. 75)
- (5) *Setimã pinima pá.* ‘Her leg is all painted up.’ (Cruz2011:0:0:41)
- (6) *Aikú suakí.* ‘I’m close to her.’ (Navarro2016:0:0:203)

The `text_source` attribute includes various types of information that help to locate the example within the original publication. The treebank sentences from Avila (2021) simply reproduce the string in the form of a bibliographic key and a page number that accompanies the dictionary examples. For instance, the primary source of the sentence in Figure 2 is de Magalhães (1876, p. 89).

To facilitate treebank usage for a wide range of purposes, we provide additional metadata. We limit our discussion here to `text_orig` and `text_prim`. Both convey the verbatim text of an example when

⁵Boldface indicates the morphemes the tokenizer splits off, as explained in Section 4.3.

it differs from the value of `text`. The `text_orig` attribute applies to an example extracted from the source identified in the `sent_id` attribute (Figure 3), while `text_prim` indicates that the source in the `sent_id` attribute is not primary (Figure 2). A total of 37.43% of the treebank sentences have one or both of these attributes, which can be relevant for training or evaluating a language detector or a spelling converter.

4.2 Annotation methodology

The construction of a treebank for one of the Indigenous languages of Brazil is particularly challenging. A total of approximately 150 languages compete for human resources to perform this task. An annotator must be familiar not only with the lexicon and grammar structure of the particular language but also with the annotation framework. It seems that the challenge has not been so appealing to the Brazilian NLP and computational linguistics communities. The treebanks referred to in Section 2 owe their existence to the participation of foreign researchers or institutions.

At first sight, it looks like UD theory only requires high school-level knowledge of traditional concepts such as parts of speech and syntactic relations, e.g., subject, object, and indirect object. Such a simplistic view will soon vanish once one starts annotating complex sentences from authentic texts and delves into the UD documentation, where one comes across non-trivial concepts such as “open clausal complement” (`xcomp`), “depictive predicate”, etc. Familiar-sounding concepts such as “indirect object”, “apposition”, or “adverbial clause” are employed in UD in a technical sense whose understanding demands a background in syntactic theory. UD’s inventory of 17 parts of speech includes categories such as particles that are not part of the traditional descriptions of Portuguese, which are generally limited to up to ten categories (Cunha and Cintra, 1985; Macambira, 1999).

The Nheengatu treebank has been annotated by a team of three non-Indigenous annotators, consisting of a senior linguist (SLIN) and two undergrad students — of whom one (EULIN) is much more experienced in the annotation task than the other (UULIN). All three are foreign-language learners of Nheengatu. SLIN and EULIN roughly possess the grammatical and lexical knowledge of de Almeida Navarro’s (2016) coursebook. UULIN is less familiar with the language but has some knowledge of Ancient Tupi. SLIN is acquainted

```

>>> import Yauti
>>> s = '''Tapiira unhehê: - Aramê/advj aikú asú. (p. 182) A anta falou: - Então estou-me indo. -
Tapiira unhehê: - Aramê a ikô xa çô.'''
>>> Yauti.parseExample(s, 'Magalhaes1876', 2, 40, 83, annotator='XXXX')
# sent_id = Magalhaes1876:2:40:83
# text = Tapiira unhehê: - Aramê aikú asú.
# text_eng = The tapir said: - Then I'm leaving.
# text_por = A anta falou: - Então estou-me indo.
# text_source = p. 182
# text_orig = Tapiira unhehê: - Aramê a ikô xa çô.
# text_annotator = XXXX
1 Tapiira tapiira NOUN N Number=Sing 6 nsubj TokenRange=0:7
2 unhehê unhehê - - - 6 - SpaceAfter=No|TokenRange
=8:14
3 : : PUNCT PUNCT - 6 punct TokenRange=14:15
4 - - PUNCT PUNCT - 6 punct TokenRange=15:16
5 Aramê aramê ADV ADVJ AdvType=Cau 6 advmod TokenRange=17:22
6 aikú ikú VERB V Number=Sing|Person=1|VerbForm=Fin 0 root
TokenRange=23:27
7 asú sú VERB V Number=Sing|Person=1|VerbForm=Fin 6 parataxi
8 - - SpaceAfter=No|TokenRange=28:31
9 . . PUNCT PUNCT - 6 punct SpaceAfter=No|TokenRange
=31:32

```

Figure 3: Analysis of a novel example with Yauti.

with most lexical and grammatical descriptions of Nheengatu, e.g., de Magalhães (1876); Sympson (1877); Stradelli (1929); Moore et al. (1994); Casanovas (2006); da Cruz (2011); Moore (2014); de Almeida Navarro (2016); Avila (2021).

We adopted the following labor division: EULIN and UULIN annotated, respectively, 165 and 45 sentences from de Almeida Navarro (2016), all of which SLIN revised, totaling 15.7% of the treebank. EULIN and UULIN also revised 46 and 29, respectively, of each other’s sentences. SLIN annotated all 1,126 remaining sentences, i.e., 84.3% of the treebank.

All sentences were first annotated with Yauti (de Alencar, 2023) and, in case of errors, manually corrected. Typically, the annotation workflow roughly consisted of the following steps: (i) select an example for annotation; (ii) format the example; (iii) apply Yauti to the formatted example; (iv) check the resulting CoNLL-U output for any remaining ambiguities and unknown words; (v) if necessary, update Yauti’s glossary and manually annotate the example with XPOS tags or token creation functions, as described in de Alencar (2023); (vi) reapply Yauti on the example; (vii) manually correct any errors; (viii) insert the serialized CoNLL-U data in the treebank file; (ix) run `validate.py` on the file and correct any detected errors. Figure 3 exemplifies the annotation of an example. The advj XPOS tag enables disambiguation. Yauti fails to recognize the second word due to a spelling mistake, the correct form being *unheẽ* ‘it says’. Yauti also renders the Portuguese translation into English by means of Google Translate using the `deep_translator` library.⁶

⁶<https://pypi.org/project/deep-translator/>

4.3 Spelling normalization, tokenization, and lemmatization

One of the factors that hinder the development of computational tools and resources for minority languages is the lack of orthography standardization (Mager et al., 2018; Ebrahimi et al., 2023). This problem especially affects both historical and contemporary Nheengatu, an exclusively oral language until very recently.⁷ On the one hand, each of the researchers that have collected oral stories, recorded dialogues, or produced vocabularies and grammar descriptions since the 19th century coined their own spelling system, e.g., Seixas (1853); de Magalhães (1876); Sympson (1877); Rodrigues (1890); Aguiar (1898); Costa (1909); de Amorim (1928); Stradelli (1929). On the other hand, ethnic, cultural, and religious heterogeneity and geographical dispersion of the speaker communities have prevented agreement on a common system or at least a reduced number of standards. As Avila (2021) observes, not only does each publication use its own orthography, but there is often variation within a single publication. Contemporary Nheengatu has far more than the four spelling systems identified by D’Angelis (2023). We looked up seven common words, e.g., pronouns and forms of *munhã* ‘to make’, across 20 publications, about half of which were by Indigenous writers, and found out that none coincides in all spellings. For example, *yam*, *yã*, and *nyã* are variants of demonstrative *nhaã* ‘that’ in some recent publications.

Orthographic variation in Nheengatu texts results from differences not only in the mapping of phonemes onto graphemes, possibly related to di-

⁷Avila’s (2021) bibliography only includes Indigenous writers from the early 2000s onward.

alectal pronunciations, but also in word segmentation. Person and number are marked by prefixes, of which there are two series, namely, the *active, dynamic* or *verbal* (IP_A) and the *inactive, stative* or *nominal* (IP_E) (Moore et al., 1994; da Cruz, 2011; Moore, 2014; Finbow, 2020). In both historical and contemporary texts, these prefixes are sometimes spelled together, sometimes separately from their heads.⁸ For example, *semayã* ‘my mother’ in one text corresponds to *se mãya, çe mãya* and *sé manha* in other texts. This sort of variation impacts many other morphemes, with the additional complication of the use of a hyphen as a separator in some texts.

To make the construction of the treebank manageable, we decided to adopt Avila’s (2021) orthographic system (henceforth AVO) due to its practical advantages. First, it provides the most comprehensive description of the language, particularly regarding the lexicon, facilitating the lexical lookup of words in the treebank. Second, Yauti heavily relies on Avila’s (2021) lexical and grammatical information. Third, AVO closely aligns with de Almeida Navarro’s (2016) orthography, allowing those teaching or learning the language with this coursebook to easily consult the treebank. The treebank already includes 216 examples directly extracted from de Almeida Navarro (2016). Finally, AVO shares many commonalities with orthographies in use by speaker communities.

Following de Almeida Navarro (2016), Avila (2021) treats the syllabic IP_E prefixes, e.g., 1st and 3rd person singular *se* and *i* in (2) and (7), respectively, as *second class pronouns*, separating them from their heads, an approach also adopted by speakers of so-called Traditional Nheengatu (Yamã et al., 2021). In (2), the IP_E functions as an agreement marker of the stative verb *katú* ‘to be fine’, while it is a pronoun realizing the internal argument of the noun *resá* ‘eyes’ in (8) and of the postposition *irumu* ‘with’ in (7) and (9). It seems that, to properly reflect the role of the IP_E as an inflectional morpheme, *se katú* ‘I’m fine’ in (2) should be treated as a single syntactic word. While syntactic words with an internal white space are, in principle, permitted, they are discouraged by the UD guidelines (Universal Dependencies). This has led us to uniformly adopt de Almeida Navarro’s (2016) and Avila’s (2021) approach, tokenizing syllabic IP_E prefixes as separate syntactic words in all situations. By contrast, both authors treat the

relational non-contiguity prefix R² and its head as a single syntactic word, e.g., *setimã* ‘her leg’ and *suakí* ‘near her’ in (5) and (6), which we also adhere to, despite the functional parallelism with the *i* IP_E, e.g., (7).

- (7) *Makití i manha usú, usú i irumu.* ‘Where his mother went, he went with her.’ (Avila2021:14:2:158) (Rodrigues, 1890, p. 233)
- (8) *Kunhã uyumuseẽ-kwáu ixé arama, aé umurí-kwáu tẽ ixé, se resá ti amuyeréu aintá i xupé, amukití aintá uikú.* ‘A woman can sweeten herself for me, she can even please me, my eyes don’t turn to her, they are turned to the other side.’ (Avila2021:0:0:87) (de Amorim, 1928, p. 366)
- (9) — *Resú-putari se irumu?* ‘“Do you want to go with me?”’ (Avila2021:53:1:696)

In a few cases, Yauti automatically splits tokens into distinct syntactic words. In (1), the content question particle *taá* fuses with the interrogative adverb *mayé* ‘how’. In (2), we have an enclitic adverb (de Almeida Navarro, 2016). Sentences (3) and (4) exemplify the clitic allomorphs of postposition *upé* ‘in’. In (8) and (9), the capability and volition auxiliaries *kwáu* ‘can’ and *putari* ‘to want’ incorporate into the main verb (da Cruz, 2011).

Avila (2021, p. 145) goes beyond a mere spelling adaptation of usage examples from the literature. He often normalizes historical variants to align with the contemporary form in Upper Rio Negro Nheengatu. For instance, in (1), the original form *reçaçáu* transforms into *resasá*, although his dictionary also registers historical variant *sasáu*. Additionally, he adjusts original punctuation to adhere to current Portuguese conventions and undertakes various interventions to enhance readability for contemporary speakers.

In the general case, Yauti automatically carries out lemmatization. It strips off the plural suffix from nouns and pronouns and the person-number prefixes from conjugated active verbs, filling in the 3rd CoNLL-U column with the appropriate lemma and encoding the morphosyntactic properties of the affix as features in the sixth column (Figures 2 and 3). Yauti’s capabilities in this domain, however, are still restricted to inflectional morphology. To parse derivational morphology, e.g., evaluative, collective, privative, and aspectual suffixes, it is

⁸This variation affects IP_E prefixes more often.

Figure 4: Relative frequency of parts of speech in UD_Nheengatu-CompLin and UD_Guajajara-TuDeT.

necessary to annotate the examples with special tags (de Alencar, 2023).

4.4 Aspects of the annotation

Of the 17 universal parts-of-speech tags (UPOS), only SYM and X have not been used because no sentence with such words has yet occurred. Usually, the tag assigned to a particular word in the treebank corresponds to Avila’s (2021) taxonomy, which mostly matches the one of da Cruz (2011). Discussing the various word classification proposals for Nheengatu is beyond the scope of this paper. We focus on property concept words (Peng, 2016), which da Cruz (2011) classifies as stative verbs. Following Moore (2014); Avila (2021), we treat these words as adjectives when they do not inflect for person and number.

Figure 4 compares the relative frequency of UPOS in UD’s Nheengatu and Guajajara treebanks. Except for adjectives, absent in the Guajajara treebank, the two tagsets coincide. The Nheengatu treebank has one feature less but much more dependency relations than the Guajajara (Table 2), which lacks, e.g., *acl:relcl*, *amod*, *cop*, *csubj*, *nmod:poss*, and *nsubj*. The two treebanks share 17 feature names, e.g., *Rel*, *Red*, and *Person[psor]* for relational prefixes, reduplication, and possessor’s person. *Clusivity* is one of the 15 feature names of Guajajara that are missing in Nheengatu, which failed to inherit this property from Tupinamba (Rodrigues, 1990, 2013). On the other hand, *Clitic*, *Compound*, *Definite*, *Deixis*, *Derivation*, *Number[psor]* and *PartType* are some of the 14 feature names of Nheengatu that are absent in Guajajara. In the UD collection, only Nheengatu pos-

sesses *Number[grnd]=Sing* and *Person[grnd]=3*, which encode the corresponding features of the internal argument of a postposition, i.e., the *landmark* or *ground* (Tosco, 2006), when it is expressed by the relational prefix R^2 , as in (6). We speculate that some of the discrepancies between the Nheengatu and Guajajara treebanks might be due to the changes the former underwent as lingua franca.

5 Parsing experiment

In this section, we report on a 10-fold cross-validation experiment with UDPipe (Straka et al., 2016; Straka and Straková, 2017). Our purpose was to assess the usefulness of the treebank for parsing, to bootstrap sentence annotation.

```

1 udpipe --train model training_file
2 udpipe --tokenize --tokenizer=ranges ↔
   ↔--accuracy --tag --parse model ↔
   ↔test_file
3 udpipe --accuracy --parse model ↔
   ↔test_file

```

Listing 1: Commands for training and testing the models.

Although UDPipe 2.0 attains better parsing results (Straka, 2018; Straka et al., 2019), due to time constraints, we limited ourselves in the experiment to the light-weight UDPipe 1.2 (Straka et al., 2016; Straka and Straková, 2017). Using the *KFold* function from the *scikit-learn* library (Pedregosa et al., 2011) with *shuffle=True* and *random_state=42* for reproducibility, we divided the treebank sentences into ten equal-sized folds, training and testing ten times, each time with a different fold as the test set and the remaining nine folds as the training set. We used the commands in Listing 1 for training and evaluating the models, which pretty much

correspond to the default settings (Straka, 2023).

While Listing 1:2 treats the test data as raw text, also performing tokenization and tagging, Listing 1:3 takes into account the gold tokenization with the gold tags. In each of the 10 executions of these commands, UDPipe 1.2. aggregates the performance results into reports like the ones in Appendix A. With Listing 1:2, accuracy in tokenization, tagging, and parsing is computed using the F1 score, i.e. the harmonic mean of precision and recall (Straka et al., 2016; Zeman et al., 2017). Tables 3 and 4 exhibit the averages of the F1 scores and standard deviations for these three dimensions computed with the NumPy library’s mean and std functions from the values of the reports generated by the ten runs of Listing 1:2. Tokenization encompasses not only splitting up text into sentences and these, in turn, into surface tokens but also two other tasks, namely, the identification of multiword tokens and syntactic words. Besides UPOS, tagging involves correctly assigning language-specific part-of-speech tags (XPOS) (Appendix B), morphological features (FEATS), and lemmas. Parsing is assessed in terms of the unlabeled attachment (UAS) and labeled attachment (LAS) scores. Table 5 presents the average UAS and LAS scores with standard deviations for parsing from gold tokenization with gold tags, computed over ten executions of Listing 1:3 as previously described. UDPipe 1.2 outperforms the rule-based Yauti morphosyntactic analyzer, which attained 80.0 and 73.2, respectively, in an analogous setting (de Alencar, 2023).

Tokenization Metric	F1 Score (%)
Tokenizer tokens	94.376 ± 1.19
Tokenizer multiword tokens	86.187 ± 10.28
Tokenizer words	94.279 ± 1.20
Tokenizer sentences	66.102 ± 4.53

Table 3: Tokenization results.

Tagging/Parsing Metric	F1 Score (%)
Tagging - UPOS	89.039 ± 1.11
Tagging - XPOS	88.16 ± 1.17
Tagging - FEATS	87.289 ± 1.17
Tagging - Lemmas	91.598 ± 1.42
Parsing - UAS	70.466 ± 1.77
Parsing - LAS	64.506 ± 1.85

Table 4: Tagging, UAS, and LAS F1 scores for parsing raw text.

	UAS (%)	LAS (%)
Average ± SD	86.30 ± 0.96	81.17 ± 1.02

Table 5: Parsing from gold tokenization with gold tags. SD = standard deviation.

6 Final remarks

We are continually revising the annotated sentences and adding new ones. We will train a model with UDPipe 2.0 to assess its impact on accelerating annotation. Given the growth rate of the UD_Nheengatu-CompLin treebank, we anticipate reaching 1800 sentences by the next UD release on May 15, 2024. A further interesting question to pursue is understanding whether the discrepancies from the other Tupian treebanks stem from Nheengatu history or theoretical preferences.

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minick Maia Alexandre and Juliana Lopes Gurgel have been carefully reviewing the annotation of a random sample of 200 sentences. Since January 2024, Juliana Lopes Gurgel has been annotating a great number of texts as part of her engagement as a scholarship holder with the DACILAT project, funded by the São Paulo State Research Support Foundation (*Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo* – FAPESP) under Process No. 22/09158-5.

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A Example parsing reports

Listings 2 and 3 display the commands of the first run of the ten-fold cross-validation, which generate the reports reproduced further below.

```
udpipe --tokenize --tokenizer=ranges ↵
      ↵--accuracy --tag --parse model1. ↵
      ↵output test1.conllu
```

Listing 2: First run of the 10-fold cross-validation: parsing from raw text.

Number of SpaceAfter=No features in gold data: 373

Tokenizer tokens - system: 1277, gold: 1313, precision: 96.01%, recall: 93.37%, f1: 94.67%

Tokenizer multiword tokens - system: 10, gold: 11, precision: 90.00%, recall: 81.82%, f1: 85.71%

Tokenizer words - system: 1287, gold: 1324, precision: 95.96%, recall: 93.28%, f1: 94.60%

Tokenizer sentences - system: 104, gold: 134, precision: 77.88%, recall: 60.45%, f1: 68.07%

Tagging from plain text (CoNLL17 F1 score) - gold forms: 1324, upostag: 90.00%, xpostag: 89.70%, feats: 88.70%, alltags: 87.09%, lemmas: 92.38%

Parsing from plain text with computed tags (CoNLL17 F1 score) - gold forms: 1324, UAS: 73.54%, LAS: 67.79%

```
udpipe --accuracy --parse model1. ↵
      ↵output test1.conllu
```

Listing 3: First run of the 10-fold cross-validation: Parsing with gold tokenization and gold tags.

Parsing from gold tokenization with gold tags - forms: 1324, UAS: 87.39%, LAS: 83.23%

B Language-specific tagset (XPOS)

XPOS	Abbreviation	Abbreviation expansion
A	adj.	first class adjective
A2	adj. 2 ^a cl.	second class adjective
ADP	postp.	postposition
ADV	adv.	adverb
ADVA	adv. manner	adverb of manner
ADVC	adv. loc.	locative adverb
ADVD	adv. dem.	demonstrative adverb
ADVDI	adv. dem. dist.	distal demonstrative adverb
ADVDX	adv. dem. prox.	proximal demonstrative adverb
ADVG	adv. gr.	degree adverb
ADVJ	adv. conj.	causal conjunctive adverb
ADV L	adv. rel.	relative adverb
ADVLA	adv. rel. man.	manner relative adverb
ADVLC	adv. rel. loc.	locative relative adverb
ADVLT	adv. rel. temp.	temporal relative adverb

Table 6: XPOS tags (part 1).

Tables 6, 7 and 8 explain UD_Nheengatu-CompLin’s language-specific part-of-speech tags (XPOS) as employed in Yauti’s full-form [lexicon](#). The second column reproduces the Portuguese abbreviations for word classes of Yauti’s [glossary](#), which are fully translated into English in the third column.

XPOS	Abbreviation	Abbreviation expansion
ADVM	adv. mod.	modal adverb
ADVNC	adv. ind. loc.	indefinite locative adverb
ADVNT	adv. ind. temp.	indefinite temporal adverb
ADVO	adv. ord.	ordinal adverb
ADVP	adv. conj. opos.	concessive conjunctive adverb
ADVR	adv. interr.	interrogative adverb
ADVRA	adv. interr. man.	manner interrogative adverb
ADVRC	adv. interr. loc.	locative interrogative adverb
ADVRT	adv. interr. temp.	temporal interrogative adverb
ADVRU	adv. interr. caus.	causal interrogative adverb
ADVS	adv. intens.	intensity adverb
ADVT	adv. temp.	temporal adverb
AFF	part. affirm.	affirmation particle
ART	art. indef.	indefinite article
ASSUM	part. assum.	assumption particle
AUXFR	aux. flex. pre.	preverbal inflected auxiliary
AUXFS	aux. flex. post.	postverbal inflected auxiliary
AUXN	aux. non-flex.	noninflected auxiliary
CARD	num. card.	cardinal numeral
CCONJ	cconj.	coordinating conjunction
CERT	part. cert.	certainty particle
CLADP	postp. encl.	enclitic postposition
CLADV	adv. encl.	enclitic adverb
COND	part. cond.	conditional particle
CONJ	conj.	conjunction
CONS	part. cons.	consent particle
COP	cop.	copula verb
CQ	part. interr. cont.	content question particle
DEM	pron. dem.	demonstrative pronoun
DEMS	pron. dem. dist.	distal demonstrative pronoun
DEMSN	pron. dem. dist. non-flex.	noninflected distal demonstrative pronoun
DEMX	pron. dem. prox.	proximal demonstrative pronoun
EMP	pron. enf.	emphasis pronoun
EXST	part. exist.	existential particle
FOC	part. focus	focus particle
FRUST	part. frust.	frustrative particle
FUT	part. fut.	future particle
IMPF	part. imperf.	imperfective particle
IND	pron. indef.	indefinite pronoun
INDQ	pron. quant.	indefinite quantifier pronoun
INT	pron. interr.	interrogative pronoun
INTJ	interj.	interjection
MOD	part. mod.	modal particle
N	s.	common noun
NEC	part. neces.	necessity deontic particle

Table 7: XPOS tags (part 2).

Tag	Abbreviation	Abbreviation expansion
NEG	part. neg.	negation particle
NEGI	part. neg. imp.	negative imperative particle
ORD	num. ord.	ordinal numeral
PART	part.	particle
PFV	part. perf.	perfective particle
PQ	part. interr. pol.	polar question particle
PREC	part. prec.	precatative particle
PREF	pref.	prefix
PREP	prep.	preposition
PRET	part. pret.	past tense particle
PRON	pron.	first class pronoun
PRON2	pron. 2 ^a cl.	second class pronoun
PROPN	s. próprio	proper noun
PROTST	part. prot.	protestative particle
PRSV	part. pres.	presentative particle
REL	pron. rel.	relative pronoun
RELF	pron. rel. livre	free relative pronoun
RPRT	part. report.	reportative particle
SCONJ	sconj.	postverbal subordinating conjunction
SCONJR	sconj. pre.	preverbal subordinating conjunction
SUFF	suf.	suffix
TOT	pron. quant. univ.	universal quantifier pronoun
TOTAL	part. tot.	totalitive particle
V	v.	first class verb
V2	v. 2 ^a cl.	second class verb
V3	v. 3 ^a cl.	third class verb
VSUFF	v. suff.	noninflectionable suffixal verb

Table 8: XPOS tags (part 3).